

Church Response to Teenage Pregnancy Among Christians in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State Nigeria

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Abstract

Teenage pregnancy is a public concern in Nigeria, with far-reaching consequences on the health, education, and economic well-being of young people. The church, as a vital institution in Nigerian society, plays a critical role in shaping attitudes and responses to teenage pregnancy. This study examines the church's response to teenage pregnancy among Christian's teenagers in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, and quantitative methods of data analysis. A total of 200 questionnaires were administered to Christian teenagers and young adults in Oyo East Local Government Area, while data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The findings revealed that churches in Oyo East Local Government Area responded to the cases of teenage pregnancy by training the church leaders to handle cases of teenage pregnancy, sensitizing pregnant teenagers. However, some churches were found to be providing support and guidance to pregnant teenagers, including counseling, emotional support, and practical assistance. The study concludes that the church's response to teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government area is complex and multifaceted, reflecting both positive and negative attitudes and practices. The study recommends that churches should provide more comprehensive and inclusive support to pregnant teenagers, and that church leaders should receive training and education on adolescent reproductive health.

Keywords: Church response, teenage pregnancy, Christians, Oyo East Local Government area, Oyo State.

Introduction

Teenage pregnancy remains a significant concern globally, with Nigeria having one of the highest rates of teenage pregnancies in sub-Saharan Africa (UNFPA, 2020). One of the salient responsibilities of women is procreation as ordained by God. However there are conditions to be met before a woman could start procreating. In the African context, the act of procreation is a responsibility of grown up young adults who have been found to be physically, socially, economically, emotionally, spiritually and psychologically matured. That is why the marriage act is highly celebrated in the present society. Nkosi (2019) perceived that, what is prevalent in both the developed and underdeveloped world is that there are girls as young as ten who are sexually active and occasionally become pregnant and give birth. In fact, the situation is such that girls between the ages of thirteen to nineteen years are now getting pregnant at an alarming rate. Surveys by investigator such as Anayochukwu (2022) and others revealed that teenagers become sexually active at an early age with corresponding high fertility. This condition is widely referred to as teenage pregnancy.

Teenage pregnancy is defined as ‘a teenager or under-aged usually within ages of thirteen to nineteen years becoming pregnant’. The term in every day speech usually refers to women who have not reached legal adulthood who become pregnant (Alabi, 2017). Teenage is often used interchangeably with adolescence. The World Health Organization (WHO) (1997) opined that, it is the period between 10 and 19 years when the secondary sex characteristics appear. Achema, Emmanuel and Moses (2015) reported that the teen years fall between the ages of 13 and 19 years. The issue of pregnancies among teenage girls seems to be one of the social problems facing not only Nigeria, but also several other nations of the world. Teenage sexual activities in Nigeria also tend to be on the increase (Nwosu, 2017). A major consequence of these increased sexual activities among teenagers is out of wedlock pregnancies that may result in abortion, childbirth or even death. Pregnancy at whatever stage in life can be a life changing experience that cuts across boundaries of race, educational attainment and socio-economic status (Alabi, 2017). Motherhood places demands on one's life which were hitherto non-existent prior to the birth of the child. When a girl that should be in school becomes pregnant, her entire life could be completely altered as her hopes and aspirations could be shattered. Teenage parents according to Alabi (2017) are parents between the ages of 13 and 19 years. Anayochukwu (2022)

believed that teenage pregnancy is a delinquent behaviour resulting from stress, dislike, malice, boredom and unhappiness experienced by a teenage girl within her home environment. Other predisposing factors include alcoholism, drug addiction, and sexual promiscuity.

According to Anayochukwu (2022) victims of teenage pregnancy lack information or probably were not adequately educated on safe-sex either by their parents, schools or development agencies that could have enabled them deal with friends who lure them into sex prematurely. He stressed further that children of single parents are more vulnerable to teenage pregnancy. In the same vein exposure to sexual content on television, sexuality in the social media, pornographic and sex chat rooms by teenagers, could most likely make them to engage in sexual activities (L'Engle, Brown and Kenneavy, 2006; Park, 2008). Acceptance of gifts for sex and evidences of some adults that deliberately take advantage of poor teenagers and encourage them into having sex were also noted as factors responsible for teenage pregnancy (United Nation, 2001). Yampolslaaya, Brown and Greenbaum (2002) affirmed that approximately 60% of adolescent mothers live in poverty at the time of the birth of their babies and “approximately 73% go on welfare within 5 years of giving birth”, the associated motherhood is characterized by shame, disgrace, and high school dropout rate which sometimes end the individual's dreams of achieving higher pursuits.

Teenage pregnancy according to Alabi (2017) is therefore a major concern to world communities with the United State being at the top with almost 1,000,000 teenage pregnancies each year. Teenage pregnancy has attracted a great deal of concern and attention from religious leaders, the general public, policymakers, and social scientists, both in the developed and less developed countries. This is especially so in Nigeria. The continuing apprehension about teenage pregnancy is based on the profound impact it can have on the lives of the girls and their children. Demographic studies continue to report that in developed countries such as the United States, Mexico, Canada, Austria, teenage pregnancy results in lower educational attainment, increased rates of poverty, and worse “life outcomes” for children of teenage mothers compared to children of young adult women (Yampolslaaya, Brown and Greenbaum, 2002) . Most teenagers do not plan their first sexual experience; rather, it is something that just happens to them based on the influence of female counterparts. Nearly 10 percent of adolescent or teenage girls get pregnant each year. Studies have found that between 20-30 percent of pregnancies in teenagers are direct results of rape, while 60% of teenage mothers have unwanted

sexual experiences preceding their pregnancies before 15 years when they were coerced by males who were at least six years older than them (Alabi, 2017).

According to Alabi (2017) a woman must be physically and medically matured before procreating. Some teenagers died or lost their babies in the process of giving birth because the body of a teenage girl is not always matured enough to handle pregnancy and the stress involved. Psychologically, the mind of a teen mother is not yet matured to handle the challenges of parenting and motherhood and this is why majority of teen mothers live with relatives who help them to cater for their babies. While teenage pregnancy is seen as aberration in some societies it is highly celebrated in some other societies as it is in line with their culture and societal norms.

The church, as a vital institution in the Nigerian society, plays a crucial role in addressing this issue. In Biblical times young people were allowed to marry with parental permission after reaching the age of accountability; twelve for girls and fourteen for boys (Gen 24:50-51). Permission was no longer required after the age of twenty-one. While there are no specific statistics available for ancient Israel, a wealth of evidence points to marriage occurring between twelve and fourteen for girls, and between fourteen and twenty for boys. Marriage at this age makes more sense when one considers that life expectancy is estimated to have been about forty years (Gen 25:20).

In the Biblical period, the penalties for sex outside of marriage were quite severe. Penalties for unmarried consensual sex included the male paying the usual dowry required and marriage if the girl's father agreed. If the father did not agree to the marriage, the dowry still had to be paid (Exodus 22:16-17). Marriage would be a logical consequence, however, to save the girl's family from shame and public humiliation. If a man raped a virgin, they were forced to marry, he had to pay the dowry, and the couple could never divorce (Deuteronomy 22:28-29). If a groom found his new bride not to be a virgin, he could complain to the elders, and if they saw the complaint as true, the woman was stoned to death in front of the home of her family to "purge this evil from their midst" (Deuteronomy 22:20-21).

In the New Testament, Christ took a much different approach. A woman was made to stand in front of Christ, having been caught in the act of adultery. The men reminded Jesus of the Law of Moses requiring she be stoned to death. Jesus said, "Let anyone among you who is without sin be the first to cast a stone." Hearing this, the men left and Jesus told the woman, "Neither do I condemn you. Go your

way and from now on do not sin again” (John 8:1-11). This study examines the church response to teenage pregnancy among Christians in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study include the following:

- i. To examine the impact of church leader’s attitudes and training on teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government Area.
- ii. To investigate the church’s response to teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government Area.
- iii. To identify support systems in response to teenage pregnancy in churches in Oyo East Local Government Area.

Research Questions

This paper will attempt most lucidly and concisely to address the following research questions:

- i. What is the impact of church leader’s attitudes and training on their response to teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government?
- ii. How do churches in Oyo East Local Government Area respond to the cases of teenage pregnancy?
- iii. What support systems do churches have in place for pregnant teenagers?

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The population for this study consists of all teenagers in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. Using simple random sampling technique, a sample of two hundred (200) teenagers and young adults were selected from the twenty (20) churches in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. A structured questionnaire comprising of 16 items developed by the researchers was administered for data collection. All items of the questionnaire were placed on a Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (4), Agreed (3), Strongly Disagreed (2), and Disagreed (1). The questionnaire was given to experts in Educational Psychology who made corrections and suggestions to ensure its face and content validity. It was also pilot tested twice at an interval of two weeks on 40 respondents in Afijio Local Government Area of Oyo State and data obtained were correlated, yielding a correlation co-efficient of 0.76 which showed that the instrument

is reliable. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while simple percentage was use to analyzed the demographic data of the respondents.

Results

The findings of the study was presented as follows:

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	84	42.0	42.0	42.0
Valid Female	116	58.0	58.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The table above reveals that 84 (42%) of the respondents are males while 116 (58%) are females.

Table 2: Age Range of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
10-19	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
20-29	144	72.0	72.0	80.0
Valid 30-39	28	14.0	14.0	94.0
40 Above	12	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows that 16 (8%) of the respondents are within the ages 10-19 years old, 144 (72%) are in the age range 20-29, 28 (14%) are within the ages of 30-39 and 12 (6%) are 40 years old and above.

Table 3: Denomination of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Othodox	80	40.0	40.0	40.0
Valid African Churches	56	28.0	28.0	68.0
Indigenous Pentecostal	64	32.0	32.0	100.0

Total	200	100.0	100.0	
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The table above reveals that 80 (40%) of the respondents are Orthodox by faith, 56 (28%) are African Indigenous Churches and 64 (32%) are Pentecostal.

Table 4: Educational Qualifications of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Primary	8	4.0	4.0	4.0
Secondary	116	58.0	58.0	62.0
Valid Tertiary	68	34.0	34.0	96.0
Others	8	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 shows educational qualification of the respondents. 8 (4%) have Primary school Leaving Certificate, 116 (58%) are secondary school graduates, 68 (34%) attended tertiary institutions while 8 (4%) have other forms of education.

Table 5: Occupation of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Unemployed	168	84.0	84.0	44.0
Valid Civil Employee	20	10.0	10.0	94.0
Private Sector Employee	12	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 reveals that 168 (84%) of the respondents are unemployed, 20 (10%) are civil service employees and 12 (6%) are private sector employees.

Table 6: Tribe of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Yoruba	176	88.0	88.0	88.0
	Hausa/Fulani	8	4.0	4.0	92.0
	Igbo	16	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

It was revealed from table 6 that 176 (88%) of the respondents are of the Yoruba tribe, 8 (4%) are Hausa/Fulani and 16 (8%) are of the Igbo tribe.

Answer to Research Questions

Research Questions 1: What is the impact of church leader’s attitudes and training on their response to teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government?

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
12	The church leaders are trained to handle cases of teenage pregnancy.	2.76	.952
13	Church leaders condemn pregnant teenagers.	2.82	1.093
14	Church leaders’ attitudes towards pregnant teenagers are supportive.	2.64	1.056
15	Church leaders receive training on adolescent reproductive health.	2.60	1.080
16	The church leaders help reduce social isolation for pregnant teenagers.	2.68	.971
	Weighted Mean	2.70	

The above table reveals a weighted mean of 2.70 out of the maximum obtainable score of 4.00 which is higher than the standard mean of 2.5. This implies that the church leaders' attitude and training has positive impact on teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government Area.

Research Questions 2: How do churches in Oyo East Local government area respond to the cases of teenage pregnancy?

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	The church provides adequate support to pregnant teenagers	2.58	.963
2	The church leaders are trained to handle cases of teenage pregnancy.	2.76	.952
3	The church helps reduce social isolation for pregnant teenagers.	2.62	.871
4	Church leaders condemn pregnant teenagers.	2.82	1.093
5	Church policies address teenage pregnancy.	2.68	.971
6	The church advocates for policies supporting pregnant teenagers.	2.52	.946
	Weighted Mean	2.66	

The above table reveals a weighted mean of 2.66 out of the maximum obtainable score of 4.00 which is slightly higher than the standard mean of 2.5. Any mean value lower than the weighted mean is not a way churches in Oyo East Local Government Area respond to the cases of teenage pregnancy. Table

7 reveals that churches in Oyo East Local Government Area respond to the cases of teenage pregnancy by training the church leaders to handle cases of teenage pregnancy, condemn pregnant teenagers and develop church policies to address teenage pregnancy. The aforementioned are the items on the table that have average means greater than the weighted mean.

Research Question 3: What support systems do churches have in place for pregnant teenagers?

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
7	The church offers counseling services to pregnant teenagers.	2.94	.970
8	Financial support is provided to pregnant teenagers by the church.	2.60	1.003
9	The church has programmes to educate teenagers on reproductive health.	3.16	.835
10	The church collaborates with community organizations to support pregnant teenagers.	2.36	1.018
11	Church members are involved in supporting pregnant teenagers.	2.70	.880
	Weighted Mean	2.75	

The above table reveals a weighted mean of 2.75 out of the maximum obtainable score of 4.00 which is higher than the standard mean of 2.5. The support systems churches have in place for pregnant teenagers are provision of counseling services to pregnant teenagers and organising programmes to educate teenagers on reproductive health. The two items on table 8 have average means greater than the weighted mean.

Discussion of the Findings

This study deals with the response of the churches to teenage pregnancy among Christians in Oyo East Local Government area, Oyo State. The first finding of this study revealed that, the church leaders' attitude and training has positive impact on teenage pregnancy in Oyo East Local Government Area. This is in tandem with the view of Jesus Christ in the New Testament, Christ took a much different approach. A woman was made to stand in front of Christ, having been caught in the act of adultery. The men reminded Jesus of the Law of Moses requiring she be stoned to death. Jesus said, "Let anyone among you who is without sin be the first to cast a stone." Hearing this, the men left and Jesus told the woman, "Neither do I condemn you. Go your way and from now on do not sin again" (John 8:1-11). This is in concomitant with Alabi (2017) who affirmed that, teenage pregnancy is a major concern to world communities with the United State being at the top with almost 1,000,000 teenage pregnancies each year. Teenage pregnancy has attracted a great deal of concern and attention from religious leaders, the general public, policymakers, and social scientists, particularly in the developed and less developed countries especially in Nigeria. The continuing apprehension about teenage pregnancy is based on the profound impact it can have on the lives of the girls and their children.

The second finding of this study revealed that churches in Oyo East Local Government Area respond to the cases of teenage pregnancy in many ways; by training church leaders on how to handle cases of teenage pregnancy, condemning pregnant teenagers and developing church policies to address teenage pregnancy. This is in concomitant with the view of Anayochukwu (2022) who believed that teenage pregnancy is a delinquent behaviour resulting from stress, dislike, malice, boredom and unhappiness experienced by a teenage girl within her home environment. Also, Nwosu (2017) was of the view that, the issue of pregnancies among teenage girls seems to be one of the social problems facing not only Nigeria, but also several other nations of the world.

The last finding revealed that, the support systems churches have in place for pregnant teenagers are provision of counseling services to pregnant teenagers and the organisation of programmes to educate teenagers on reproductive health. The two items on table 9 have average means greater than the weighted mean. There is need for counselling services and education for teenagers on reproductive health as affirmed by Alabi (2017) that, pregnancy at whatever stage in life can be a life changing experience that cuts across boundaries of race, educational attainment and socio-economic status.

Motherhood places demands on one's life which were hitherto non-existent prior to the birth of the woman. When a girl that should be in school becomes pregnant, her entire life could be completely altered as her hopes and aspirations could be shattered. The finding also aligns with Anayochukwu (2022) who noted that, victims of teenage pregnancy lacked information or probably were not adequately educated on safe-sex either by their parents, schools or development agencies that could have enabled them deal with friends who lure them into sex prematurely. In the same vein exposure to sexual content on television, sexuality in the social media, pornographic and sex chat rooms by teenagers, could most likely make them to engage in sexual activities (L'Engle, Brown and Kenneavy, 2006; Park, 2008).

Conclusion

The response of the church to teenage pregnancy among Christians in Oyo East Local Government area of Oyo State is a complex and multifaceted issue. The findings of this study have shown that the church's response to teenage pregnancy is influenced by a variety of factors, including the denomination of the church, the level of education of church leaders, and the church's teachings on sexuality. Despite these factors, the study has also shown that many churches in Oyo East Local Government area are not providing adequate support to pregnant teenagers. Many of the respondents reported feeling stigmatized and judged by their churches, and some even reported being denied communion or other sacraments. This lack of support can have serious consequences for the health and well-being of pregnant teenagers, and can also perpetuate the cycle of poverty and inequality.

The findings also highlight the need for churches to provide more comprehensive and inclusive support to pregnant teenagers. This can include providing counseling and emotional support, as well as practical assistance such as food, clothing, and shelter. Churches can also play a critical role in promoting education and awareness about teenage pregnancy, and in advocating for policies and programs that support pregnant teenagers. The church's response to teenage pregnancy among Christians in Oyo East Local Government area of Oyo State is a critical issue that requires urgent attention. Churches have a unique role to play in providing support and guidance to pregnant teenagers, and in promoting education and awareness about teenage pregnancy. By working together, churches and other stakeholders can help to reduce the stigma and shame associated with teenage pregnancy, and can promote more positive and supportive responses to this critical issue.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Churches should provide more comprehensive and inclusive support to pregnant teenagers, including counseling, emotional support, and practical assistance.
2. Churches should promote education and awareness about teenage pregnancy, and should advocate for policies and programmes that support pregnant teenagers.
3. Churches should work to reduce the stigma and shame associated with teenage pregnancy, and promote more positive and supportive responses to this critical issue.
4. Church leaders should receive training and education on adolescent reproductive health, including teenage pregnancy.
5. Church leaders should provide spiritual counselling and guidance to teenage mothers by emphasizing God's love, forgiveness and redemption.

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